

Frequency Separated Periodic Block Bootstrapping of US COVID-19 Death Rate Periodic Components

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Abstract

Following the identification of the first confirmed case of COVID-19 in the United States on January 20th, 2020, and the World Health Organization's pandemic declaration on March 11th, 2020, there is ongoing interest in characterizing the seasonality of the SARS-CoV-2 virus and its effects. This study uses novel Frequency Separated Periodic Block Bootstrap (FSPBB) methods to investigate periodically correlated components such as seasonality within US COVID-19 death rates. When time series data are potentially composed of multiple periodically correlated components, separation of periodic or cyclostationary processes by frequency is necessary to properly bootstrap those characteristics. Compared to other block bootstrap strategies for cyclostationary processes, FSPBB is shown to typically perform better in the identification, separation, and estimation of the sampling distribution of characteristics of both individual and multiple cyclostationary processes with strong robustness against noisy data. Results from the FSPBB analysis of the periodic characteristics of US COVID-19 Death Rates are provided and compared against results from alternative bootstrapping methods.

Key Words: Frequency Separated Periodic Block Bootstrap, COVID-19 SARS-CoV-2 United States Death Rates, Seasonal Mean and Periodic characteristics, Multiple Periodically Correlated Time Series, Cyclostationary Process Frequency Interference, Kolmogorov-Zurbenko Iterated Moving Average, Spatio – Temporal Analysis Frequency Separation

1. Introduction

In 2020 the SARS-CoV-2, or COVID-19, virus became and continues to be a significant global health concern. As the virus has transitioned over time from a global pandemic to a persistent endemic there is strong interest in the seasonal component of the disease. A better understanding of the seasonality of COVID-19 can provide insight and useful tools for emergency preparedness, public health communication, allocation of resources, and prediction. With a continuously growing timeline of now over, approximately, three years of data there is increasing opportunity to research the cyclostationary or periodically correlated (PC) time series components such as seasonality of COVID-19. This research investigates the seasonal PC component of COVID-19 deaths in the United States using a novel non-parametric resampling method called Frequency Separated Periodic Block Bootstrapping (FSPBB) producing confidence intervals for the seasonal mean.

A brief timeline of COVID-19 can be found from the Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) Museum COVID-19 Timeline (2023) and begins in December 2019 with what would become known as the SARS-CoV-2, or COVID-19, virus emerging in Wuhan, in China's Hubei Province. By January 14, 2020 the World Health Organization (WHO) has the first evidence of possible human-to-human transmission of the SARS-CoV-2 virus. On January 20, 2020 CDC reports the first laboratory-confirmed case in the U.S. Spreading rapidly, by March 11, 2020, with in excess of 118,000 cases in 114 countries and 4,291 deaths, the WHO declares COVID-19 a pandemic. In the US, a nationwide emergency declaration is issued on March 13, 2020. Towards the present, the WHO ends the COVID-19 global health emergency on May 5, 2023, and by May 11, 2023 the US COVID-19 public health emergency declaration ends. During this time there are approximately 6.8 million deaths globally from COVID-19. As of July 1, 2023 there are approximately 1.135 million recorded deaths in the US from COVID-19. Despite the end of the emergency declarations, in July 2023 there are approximately 8000 US weekly hospital admissions, 1% of Emergency Department visits are diagnosed with COVID and there are approximately 500 weekly deaths according to the CDC COVID Data Tracker (2023).

Resampling with replacement from a sample of data, or bootstrapping, is useful to estimate the sampling distribution of statistics such as the mean. This replicates the sampling variability which allows for production of bootstrapped confidence intervals. The process of random sampling with replacement from a sampled data results in independent draws that form a resample of the same length as the original data set and was first detailed by Efron (1979). Time series data behave differently than typical sample data since successive data points, or observations, are ordered in time. More on time series including definitions, notation, and examples can be found in Wei (1990). Often, ordered data points may be correlated with prior observations in the time series. Consequently, independently sampling data points from the dataset to form a new ordered resample will not replicate any correlations between a given and prior data points within the original time series. The correlation between successive time series data points is destroyed. Special bootstrapping methods are needed to prevent the destruction of correlation structures within time series data. Block bootstrapping is a class of methods which attempt to replicate and preserve correlations in spatio-temporal data. Block bootstrapping often involves a general strategy of splitting the time series into blocks and then randomly sampling the blocks to form the resamples. An example of this is the Moving Block Bootstrap first introduced by Kunsch (1989). This can help replicate the correlation structure between given data points and some prior observations within the limits of the block size. Clearly, correlations between data points separated by more than the length of the bootstrapped blocks will have correlation structures destroyed.

When time series data are cyclic, cyclostationary, or periodic in nature such as seasonality when referring to the annual cycle, they possess a component with a given period, p , exhibit strong correlations between data points that are kp time points separated, where $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ is an integer multiple. Block bootstrapping has difficulty reproducing the correlation structure of PC time series. As previously described, block bootstrapping with any block lengths less than the given period, p , will eliminate these correlations. Additionally, bootstrapping with block lengths greater than the given period, p , will preserve the correlation within each block; however, there is no reason randomly sampled adjacent blocks will retain synchronicity in the periodic correlation structure when forming the resample. For example, there is no guarantee the first data point of a resampled block to be the next step in each cycle of period p that follows the last data point of the prior resampled

block. For this reason, many block bootstrapping strategies are not well suited for PC time series.

A seasonal block bootstrap was proposed by Politis (2001) where the block length is restricted to be a multiple of the period p . Regardless of whichever step in the cycle a block begins, all other blocks in the resample will likewise start and end with a common step in the cycle of period p . This strategy will preserve correlation structures between data points that are p points removed from each other in time series data. Some other block bootstrapping methods for PC time series include those presented by Chan et al. (2004) and the general seasonal block bootstrap (GSBB) by Dudek et al. (2014). While the block bootstrap methods described above, which can collectively be referred to as periodic block bootstrap (PBB) methods, attempt to preserve the PC correlation structure, these strategies also bootstrap any additional components including the noise present in the time series. Unsurprisingly, even modest levels of noise can widen bootstrapped confidence intervals for measures such as the PC component period mean more than the supposed confidence interval level. We propose the novel frequency separated periodic block bootstrap (FSPBB) which simulation has shown tends to yield smaller confidence intervals (CI) for sample statistics than PBB methods, and with greater coherence to the true unknown population parameter of interest, such as the seasonal mean, than PBB methods. This study analyses PC components of United States COVID-19 death rates using both GSBB and FSPBB. CI size is compared between the methods for the periodic means of the select PC components. In general, FSPBB outperforms GSBB resulting in smaller CI size on average for the periodic means of the PC components of US COVID-19 death rates.

2. Methods

2.1 Existing Methods and Challenge

In many real-world situations, such as COVID-19, the time series is a function of the accumulated influence of multiple components, such as a noise or random error component in addition to the PC component. While the PBB methods described above attempt to preserve one PC correlation structure, these strategies also bootstrap any additional components including the noise component, including other PC components of different periods. Figure 1 illustrates the PBB method for the PC component and any other components, represented as a noisy signal, in the PC time series.

Figure 1: Illustration of resampling a PC time series with PC component A of period p_A , and a different component B that is not PC of period p_A , with a PBB strategy incorporating p_A .

the period p_A in the design of block length, replicating the PC structure of component A while simultaneously resampling component B.

2.2 FSPBB Approach

The objective is to bootstrap the PC time series component alone to preserve the correlation structures of the PC component while not bootstrapping other unrelated components that are not periodic at the given period of the PC component. A solution is drawn from the periodogram, which is a spectral density or frequency domain representation of a time series and is described in Wei (1989), and iterated moving average bandwidth filters of Zurbenko (1986). Components operating at different frequencies, or the reciprocal of period, may sum in the time domain but share no correlation. In this way, different frequencies operate independently. Filtering a PC time series according to its spectral density by separating a PC component by its frequency, would create a new PC time series composed primarily of the component PC of interest, while preserving the PC component correlation structure. The new component PC time series could then be block bootstrapped with the appropriate block size to preserve that correlation structure. This approach, or frequency separated periodic block bootstrapping (FSPBB), preserves the desired correlation structures within a PC time series while greatly reducing bootstrapping of uncorrelated components. This strategy is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Illustration of resampling a PC time series with PC component A of period p_A , and a different component B that is not PC of period p_A . After PC component filtration and separation, FSPBB incorporates the period, p_A in the design of block length for block bootstrapping to replicating the PC structure of component A while limiting replication of much of the non-PC structure of component B.

In FSPBB it is necessary to separate and filter the PC time series by portions of the spectral density; what is passed through the filter contains the PC component frequency. This can be accomplished by applying a bandpass filter to pass a narrow band of frequencies around the corresponding frequency of the PC component, while frequencies outside this band, the stopband, are attenuated. The KZFT filter, an extension of iterated moving averages or Kolmogorov-Zurbenko (KZ) filters, is one such band pass filter.

KZ filters and their extensions can separate portions of the frequency domain to exclude interfering frequencies as detailed in Yang and Zurbenko (2010). These filters have natural uses to isolate frequencies in a variety of fields such as the environmental sciences, meteorology, economics, public health, and climatology. Examples include investigating

ozone in Tsakiri and Zurbenko (2010), air quality in Kang et al. (2013), global temperature in Ming and Zurbenko (2012), atmospherics in Zurbenko and Potrzeba (2010), climate in Zurbenko and Cyr (2011), and diabetes in Arndorfer and Zurbenko (2017). The frequency separated component can then independently be investigated to reveal important details about patterns and processes often hidden within the original data, as well as associations with possible factors operating at similar spatio-temporal scales. This is the idea behind spatio-temporal analysis by frequency separation (STAFS). A novel example of this applied to skin cancer is extensively explored in Valachovic and Zurbenko (2013, 2014). Frequency separation is used to identify hidden PC components in a skin cancer time series and then to perform multivariate analysis on these component factors in Valachovic and Zurbenko (2017). FSPBB adapts the use of frequency separation prior to analysis and applies it to a bootstrap design for PC time series. Also, the parameters of the filter provide a clear and direct explanation relating to their use in FSPBB.

2.3 FSPBB Bandwidth Filters and Bootstrapping

The Kolmogorov-Zurbenko (KZ) filter is the iteration of a simple central moving average defined in Zurbenko (1986). It is a filter with two parameters m , and k . The parameter m , a positive odd integer, is the filter window length and the parameter k , a positive integer, is the number of iterations. KZ filters are low pass filters that strongly attenuate signals of frequency $1/m$ and higher while passing lower frequencies, smoothing the time series. Applied to a random process $\{X(t): t \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ a KZ filter with m time points, and k iterations is defined as:

Equation 1: Kolmogorov-Zurbenko Filter

$$KZ_{m,k}(X(t)) = \sum_{u=-k(m-1)/2}^{k(m-1)/2} \frac{a_u^{m,k}}{m^k} X(t+u)$$

The coefficients $a_u^{m,k}$ are the polynomial coefficients from:

$$\sum_{r=0}^{k(m-1)} z^r a_{r-k(m-1)/2}^{m,k} = (1 + z + \dots + z^{m-1})^k$$

One advantage of the KZ filter is the computational ease with which statistical software can apply it in an iterated form. As an application of k iterations of a moving average filter of m time points, the KZ filter can be produced according to the following algorithm:

Equation 2: KZ filter as an iterated algorithm

$$KZ_{m,1}(X(t)) = \sum_{u=-(m-1)/2}^{(m-1)/2} \frac{a_u^{m,1}}{m^1} X(t+u) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{u=-(m-1)/2}^{(m-1)/2} X(t+u)$$

$$KZ_{m,2}(X(t)) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{u=-k(m-1)/2}^{k(m-1)/2} KZ_{m,1}(X(t+u))$$

$$\vdots$$

$$KZ_{m,k}(X(t)) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{u=-k(m-1)/2}^{k(m-1)/2} KZ_{m,k-1}(X(t+u))$$

The transfer function is the linear mapping describing how input frequencies are transferred to outputs. The energy transfer function is the square of the transfer function and as such is symmetric about zero. The energy transfer function of the KZ filter at frequency λ is seen in the following equation. This shows how with only a few iterations, a KZ filter, strongly attenuates signals of frequency $1/m$ and higher while passing lower frequencies:

Equation 3: KZ energy transfer function

$$|B(\lambda)|^2 = \left(\frac{\sin(\pi m \lambda)}{m \sin(\pi \lambda)} \right)^{2k}$$

The cut-off frequency is a limit or boundary at which the energy transferred through a filter is suppressed or diminished rather than allowed to pass through. The point where output power is $\alpha \in (0,1)$ times that of the input can be used as the boundary. It is common to use $\alpha = 1/2$ or the half power point, a power ratio in $10 * \log_{10}$ of -3 decibels units. The cut-off frequency for the transfer function for a KZ filter is:

Equation 4: KZ cut-off frequency

$$\lambda_0 \approx \frac{\sqrt{6}}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{1 - (1/2)^{\frac{1}{2k}}}{m^2 - (1/2)^{\frac{1}{2k}}}}$$

Where the KZ filter is a low pass filter, strongly filtering signals of a frequency at or above the frequency equivalent to $1/m$, and may be useful for isolating low frequencies, the related Kolmogorov-Zurbenko Fourier Transform (KZFT) filter is a band pass filter. KZFT is a filter applied to a random process $\{X(t): t \in T\}$ having three parameters: m time points, k iterations, and shifted center at a frequency ν . The KZFT is defined:

Equation 5: Kolmogorov-Zurbenko Fourier Transform

$$KZFT_{m,k,\nu}(X(t)) = \sum_{u=-k(m-1)/2}^{k(m-1)/2} \frac{a_u^{m,k}}{m^k} e^{-i2m\nu u} X(t+u)$$

The coefficients $a_u^{m,k}$ are the polynomial coefficients from:

$$\sum_{r=0}^{k(m-1)} z^r a_{r-k(m-1)/2}^{m,k} = (1 + z + \dots + z^{m-1})^k$$

Where the KZ filter is symmetric around zero, the KZFT is a symmetric band pass filter around frequency ν . Practical use of the KZFT filter is similar to the KZ filter since it can be produced in statistical software. The energy transfer function of the KZFT filter at a frequency λ with parameters m , k , and ν is given below.

Equation 6: Kolmogorov-Zurbenko Fourier Transform energy transfer function

$$|B(\lambda - \nu)|^2 = \left(\frac{\sin(\pi m (\lambda - \nu))}{m \sin(\pi (\lambda - \nu))} \right)^{2k}$$

It follows that the cut off frequency is:

Equation 7: Kolmogorov-Zurbenko Fourier Transform cut-off frequency.

$$|\lambda_0 - \nu| \approx \frac{\sqrt{6}}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{1 - (1/2)^{\frac{1}{2k}}}{m^2 - (1/2)^{\frac{1}{2k}}}}$$

For these filters, the cut-off frequency boundaries then become useful to determine the region of the spectra passed and those stopped, suppressed, or filtered.

KZFT filters are used prior to block bootstrapping methods to separate the PC component in PC time series. The parameter ν is the easiest to interpret since it is the frequency around which the filter will be centered, and will be set to $1/p$, the reciprocal of the period p of the PC component of interest. The KZFT filter is symmetric around frequency ν . The KZ filter parameter m defines the width of the moving average filter window. It can be interpreted as defining the endpoints of the filter width, where the energy transfer through the filter is zero. The effect of varying the KZ filter parameter m is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: One side of the symmetric energy transfer functions for KZFT filters centered at frequency λ_0 with parameters $\nu = \lambda_0$, $k = 1$ and (A) $m = 3$ in red, (B) $m = 5$ in orange, (C) $m = 11$ in green, and (D) $m = 101$ in blue.

The KZ filter parameter k defines the number of iterations of the moving average filter performed. It can be interpreted as defining the taper of the filter and it can move the filter cut-off even though it does not change the filter endpoints where the time series energy is completely attenuated. The effect of varying the KZ filter parameter k , for a constant fixed m , is illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Energy transfer functions and KZFT filters centered at λ_0 for parameters m , such that $\frac{1}{m} = \lambda_0 - \lambda_1 = \lambda_2 - \lambda_0$ and $k = 1$ in red with cut-off (A), $k = 2$ in orange with cut-off (B), $k = 10$ in green with cut-off (C), $k = 100$ in blue with cut-off (D).

Proper parameter choice of a KZFT filter which is then applied to a PC time series attenuates frequencies lying outside of a narrow band around a specific PC component frequency. The resultant PC component time series is now primarily composed of the PC correlation structure.

After PC component separation, the FSPBB approach then block bootstraps the PC component time series rather than the original PC time series. The General Seasonal Block Bootstrap (GSBB) of Dudek et al. (2014) is chosen as a representative of PBB methods. The GSBB bootstraps the original time series and does not benefit from frequency separation. GSBB is presented as a comparison for FSPBB, which block bootstraps the frequency separated PC component. The bootstrapping process for a given period, p , and a time series of n observations is done by creating p exclusive and exhaustive subsets, each composed of one of the first p observations, and the integer multiple observations of that first observation. Each resample is formed by randomly selecting with replacement from the p ordered subsets in succession, repeated until n observations are selected. The bootstrap then repeats this process for a large number, k , of resamples. The periodic means, or the means at each time point throughout a cycle of period p are calculated for each resample, providing an estimate of the sampling distribution for that statistic. Finally, the k resamples permit production of 95% confidence intervals around the periodic mean using the 0.025 and 0.975 quantiles of the bootstrapped means.

2.4 Data Sources and Analysis

COVID-19 deaths are recorded daily, are compiled from the CDC, state, and local public health agencies and the time series is available at USAFacts (2023). These data are changed to death rates per 100 thousand after adjusting for population with data available from the United States Census Bureau (2023). The US COVID-19 death rate time series is seen in Figure 5. Analysis is performed in R version 4.1.1 (2013) statistical software and uses the KZFT function in the KZA package as detailed in Close and Zurbenko (2013). In this analysis, FSPBB uses KZFT parameters of $m = 181$, $k = 1$, and $v = 1/365$ to bandwidth the 365 day or 1-year seasonal PC component. The parameters of $m = 105$, $k = 1$, and

$\nu = 1/7$ are used to bandwidth the 7-day weekly PC component. Both GSBB and FSPBB methods bootstrap 10000 resamples for these PC components.

Figure 5: US COVID-19 death rate time series

3. Results

While interest is primarily focused on the 365-day periodic, or seasonal mean, the FSPBB approach indicates that we must first separate out other PC component periods with strong variation in addition to noise. These components themselves may be of interest and FSPBB can produce CI for their PC mean if there is one. For example, the weekly mean appears to exhibit strong periodic fluctuation, and FSPBB 95% CI for the weekly mean ranges from approximately (0.007, 0.250) additional deaths per 100K population to (-0.014, -0.219) per 100K population within the weekly cycle. For comparison, on average the GSBB CI size is 4.9 times larger than the FSPBB CI size. Figure 6 illustrates the 95% bootstrapped CI size for the weekly mean using the GSBB in red and the FSPBB in blue across typical 7-day cycles.

Figure 6: 95% CI for the US COVID-19 death rate 7-day, or weekly, mean from GSBB in red and FSPBB in blue.

Of particular interest due to the public health implications, the FSPBB 95% CI for the seasonal mean ranges from approximately (0.119, 0.907) per 100 thousand population to a low of (0.069, 0.379) per 100 thousand population. On average, the GSBB CI size is 1.1 times larger than the FSPBB CI size. Figure 7 illustrates the 95% bootstrapped CI size for the seasonal mean comparing the GSBB in red and the FSPBB in blue across typical 365-day in the seasonal cycles.

Figure 7: 95% CI for the US COVID-19 death rate 365-day, yearly, or seasonal mean from GSBB in red and FSPBB in blue.

4. Discussion

On average the 95% CI for the weekly mean from the GSBB is 4.9 times larger than that from the FSPBB. Furthermore, the 95% CI for the weekly mean from GSBB fails to exclude 0, where the 95% CI for the weekly mean from FSPBB does exclude 0 at the peaks and valleys of the 7-day cycle, providing evidence of the significance of this PC component. The coefficient of determination, or R^2 , between the weekly PC component and the original time series is approximately 0.10 indicating that the weekly PC component accounts for approximately 10% of the total variability in the US COVID-19 death rate time series. This FSPBB 95% CI indicates that there is evidence of a fluctuation in the weekly mean from a peak of approximately (0.007, 0.250) additional deaths per 100 thousand population to weekly low of (-0.014, -0.219), or (0.014, 0.219) fewer deaths per 100 thousand population. This weekly PC component may be less related to some natural phenomenon and more related to reporting or other administrative processes. Still, it is informative and critical to investigate this PC component separately through FSPBB from that of the seasonal component.

There are times during the seasonal cycle where the GSBB CI is smaller than that from the FSPBB, but there are more times, and with a greater difference where the FSPBB CI size is smaller than that from the GSBB. On average the 95% CI for the seasonal mean from the GSBB is 1.1 times larger than that from the FSPBB. This improvement in CI size for FSPBB is more modest than for the weekly PC component. However, the 95% CI for the seasonal mean from GSBB often fails to exclude 0, where the 95% CI for the weekly mean from FSPBB excludes 0 throughout the 365-day cycle, again providing strong evidence of

the significance of the seasonal PC component. The general smaller CI size from the FSPBB is providing greater evidence of the significance of seasonality, the timing of COVID-19 waves, and the strength of seasonally affected periods. The FSPBB 95% CI indicates that the seasonal mean ranges from a high daily death rate of (0.119, 0.907) per 100 thousand population in January to a mid April low of (0.069, 0.379) per 100 thousand population. The coefficient of determination, or R^2 , between the seasonal PC component and the original time series is approximately 0.56 indicating that the seasonal PC component accounts for approximately 56% of the total variability in the US COVID-19 death rate time series. Together, the seasonal and weekly PC components (and a limited bandwidth of frequencies adjacent), are accounting for approximately 66% of the total variability in the US COVID-19 death rate time series.

While the GSBB, and more generally PBB, methods have some success preserving the PC component correlation structure, FSPBB tends to have better performance. For bootstrapping statistics such as the periodic mean of the PC component in this time series, the GSBB CI size is generally larger, sometimes significantly, than that produced by FSPBB. FSPBB has several limitations in its design in comparison to other PBB methods. FSPBB performance is tied to selection of parameters used for filtration and results may differ depending on choice for PC component estimation for the US COVID-19 data. Also, since FSPBB methods rely upon filtering the original PC time series with the application of moving averages, the observations at the ends of the time series will have the filter incompletely applied. For this reason, FSPBB generally requires greater quantities data than PBB. With only a little over three years of COVID-19 data, PBB and FSPBB methods are at their limits bootstrapping a seasonal component. Therefore, these results should be viewed as preliminary. Additional data is likely to improve performance, and we recommend that additional research continue as more data becomes available. Finally, this work investigates two of the most prominent and interesting PC components of the US COVID-19 death rate. A last recommendation is for additional research to better characterize other COVID-19 PC components. A more complete analysis of the PC components of COVID-19 in the US using FSPBB may offer further benefits to public health, preparedness, and prediction.

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